

BUA 60MW HYDROPOWER PROJECT

Isaac Chitedze

E-mail: ichitedze@pml.mw

Energy Modelling Platform for Africa (EMP-A)

2023

Context, and Aim

Access to electricity (base year 2022): 18%

- National Grid: 11.4%
- Off-grid systems: 6.6%
- Urban areas: 58%
- Rural areas: 4%

Installed Capacity: 566.5 MW

- Hydroelectric: 401 MW
- Solar: 101 MW
- Biomass: 18.5 MW
- Diesel: 46 MW

Aim

- Under-generation & delayed generation capacity expansion- Malawi's projected demand in 2023 is 941MW
- The aim is to assess the financial viability of 60MW Bua hydropower project to supply power to the grid and the end-user electricity tariff.

Fig 1: Hydropower potential sites in Malawi

Project Description and Financing

An Independent Power Producer (IPP) intends to develop 60MW hydropower at Bua River in Malawi and sell to the grid through a Power Purchase Agreement (PPA)

- Plant size: 60 MW installed capacity
- Star year: 2023
- Construction period: 3 years
- First year operation: 2026
- PPA term: 25 years (operation period)
- Yearly production: 300 GWh
- Discount rate: 10%
- Inflation rate: 13%

Depreciation: 20 years linear

Interest Rate: 10% (P+I)

O&M Cost: 10 million annually

Project Finance Structure

■ Equity Financing ■ Debt Financing

Scenarios Analysis

Using the FINPLAN model, the following financial scenarios were analysed:

Scenario	Scenario Description	Key Assumptions
Normal	Non-cost-reflective tariff	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Subsidies or rebate -Constant electricity price
Worst	Construction delay	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Few financing options (more expensive) -Increase the cost of investment (equipment etc.- 20% increase) -High inflation rate (10% higher)
Best	Cost-reflective tariff (Automatic Tariff adjustment Formula [ATAF])	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Stable exchange rate -Steady inflation rate -No force majeure

Results

Best Scenario

Annual PPA Tariff Escalation

Bua Hydro- Project Finance Analysis

NPV: USD 18152m

IRR: 13%

Loan Repayment period: 12 years

PPA initial tariff: USD 0.045 per kwh (annual price escalation in addition to inflation)

Results

Worst Scenario

Annual PPA Tariff Escalation

Bua Hydro- Project Finance Analysis

NPV: USD 32111m
 IRR: 15%

PPA initial tariff: USD 0.054 per kWh (annual price escalation in addition to inflation)

PPA final year tariff: 3.577 per kWh

Less cash available during loan term

Conclusions and Policy Insights

Conclusion

- The Bua 60MW hydropower project is financially viable and would contribute significantly to the energy policy goal of increasing the renewable generation capacity in the country and achieving universal energy access.
- The best-case scenario tariff in the first year of operation is \$0.045 per kWh while the worst-case scenario is \$0.054 per kWh due to high inflation.

Policy Insight

- Under-generation challenge can be address by attracting more Independent Power Producers (private sector investment) through competitive bidding to drive down the PPA tariffs.
- To instill confidence in IPPs the country must implement cost-reflective tariff.